

Persona-Catalogue

Personas for the Application of
Easy Reading in Different Contexts

EVE4all-Project

4th extended Edition – June 2024

(Translation of the [German version](#))

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1. Introduction

In software development, personas are used to design accessible and user-oriented technologies. Personas are fictional individuals or end-users with real needs, abilities, and goals (Nielsen 2019). Working with this method allows developers and project stakeholders to deeply engage with the end-users of their products and their life situations. Personas can also be used in other contexts to empathise with user groups and understand the needs, opportunities, and barriers that may arise when using technologies and media (Billestrup et al. 2014).

Within the research project "EVE4all - Easy Understanding for All" at the Technical University of Dortmund, personas are utilised. The project aims to validate the Easy Reading Add-on – a free Add-on that enables people with various support needs to use websites independently. While personas are typically used in the development process, in the EVE4all project, personas were (further) developed to demonstrate potential application examples and contexts for Easy Reading to potential partners. Some of the personas were developed as part of a project study by students of the bachelor's program Rehabilitation Pedagogy at the TU Dortmund University and further refined by the EVE4all project team. Personas are used here for acquisition purposes and to identify opportunities and risks associated with using digital technology in (rehabilitation) pedagogical contexts.

The personas developed in the project context are presented in this "Persona Catalogue." The catalogue includes 16 different personas representing various types of users. Fourteen of the personas are potential end-users. The personas are consistently structured, providing demographic information such as age or gender, sketching the persona's character, hobbies, and other life circumstances. In addition to the 14 end-users, two personas were developed to represent potential specialists or multipliers.

A special feature is the presentation of digital barriers, and participation desires that Easy Reading aims to eliminate or enable. This allows personas to be used to demonstrate the diversity of the target audience and the various applications of software (in this case, Easy Reading).

You can visit the [website](#) for more information about Easy Reading and the EVE4all project.

2. What are Personas?

Personas are fictional characters or archetypes created to be considered realistic (Nielsen 2019). They are based on relevant information from potential and real users and are frequently used in marketing or for the development of software and medical devices (Akre et al. 2019; Chaniaud et al. 2021; Dirks 2020; Haag and Marsden 2019; Kirchem and Waack 2021; Majumder et al. 2020; Neate et al. 2019; Nielsen 2019; Volz and Griep 2020; Song et al. 2020; Terho et al. 2022). Personas represent specific target groups and share the same characteristics, traits, social environments, and circumstances as the group they represent (Kirchem and Waack 2021; Nielsen 2019). To create a persona, these characteristics and other attributes of the target group must be researched and developed. Characteristics can be categorized into demographic and psychographic categories. However, other categories can be created depending on which features are important for a specific persona (Kirchem and Waack 2021).

Personas should be developed to reflect the focused target group (Kirchem and Waack 2021). The motivation of the persona is a central element in this regard. Motivations can be formulated both positively and negatively. Through personas, developers and designers can gain a better understanding of the diversity of their target group or end-users. Furthermore, developers and designers can better capture their end-users' actual needs and desires, thus focusing the development process on them (Dirks 2020). In this way, better design decisions can be made, and the features of the end product can be developed more precisely to meet the needs of the end-users (Billestrup et al. 2014; Grudin and Pruitt 2002; Haag and Marsden 2019; Marsden and Haag 2016; Miaskiewicz and Kozar 2011; Pröbster et al. 2019; Singh 2018). The use of personas with disabilities can also support the fulfilment of requirements for accessible software (Zimmermann and Vanderheiden 2008).

Personas played a central role in the development of Easy Reading (Dirks 2020). In the project, personas with disabilities were used to raise awareness among developers about the needs of these groups of people to develop software that caters to their needs and desires. The method of personas was also employed for the EVE4all project to provide potential collaborators with examples of the use of Easy Reading in their facilities.

3. Personas

When using the internet, various barriers can arise that can hinder successful internet use:

- Technical and functional barriers
- Editorial and content-related barriers
- Barriers due to the design of user interfaces
- Organizational barriers

(Berger et al. 2011, 133)

The personas in this catalogue encounter "editorial and content-related barriers" and "barriers due to design" while using the internet (Berger et al. 2011, 133). Technical and functional barriers have been excluded here because Easy Reading does not provide corresponding tools and only offers support at the content level.

To systematize the personas, they are divided according to these two types of barriers. However, this division should not suggest that one can only encounter one type of barrier. It is simply intended to increase the clarity of the persona catalogue. The two personas that outline multipliers or professionals are assigned to the overarching category of organization and environment.

3.1 Overview of the Personas

Tools	Personas using the tool
<p>Reading aloud</p> <p>You can have the text read aloud to you. There are various voice options to choose from. The text can also be read at different speeds.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dieter • Justin • Kristine • Lisa • Paul • Ramona • Robert • Samantha • Jutta
<p>Reading mode</p> <p>Only the important content of a page is displayed. Unnecessary images are hidden.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amir • Dieter • Eberhart • Kristine • Lisa • Paul • Ramona • Robert • Rolf • Samantha • Jutta

Tools	Personas using the tool
<p>Reading ruler</p> <p>With the reading ruler, you stay on your current line. The text of the current line is highlighted, and the rest of the text is greyed out.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amir • Dieter • Eberhart • Gerda • Kristine • Lisa • Paul • Ramona • Robert • Samantha • Jutta
<p>Change colour</p> <p>You can change the background colour and text colour on a website.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gerda • Robert • Gertrud
<p>Enlarge/reduce font size</p> <p>You can increase or decrease the font size of the text on a website.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dieter • Gerda • Robert • Gertrud
<p>Increase/reduce line spacing</p> <p>You can increase or reduce the line spacing of the text on a website.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dieter • Robert
<p>Symbol language</p> <p>Symbol language helps with reading and understanding. The text is supplemented with symbols.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amir • Dieter • Lisa • Rolf
<p>Symbol search</p> <p>You can display a matching symbol for a selected word. The symbol can help you understand the word better.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amir • Lisa • Rolf • Dieter
<p>Image search</p> <p>You can display a matching image for a selected word. The image can help you understand the word better.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lisa
<p>Word explanation</p> <p>You can get words explained. When you click on a word, a short text appears that provides a more detailed explanation of the word.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Eberhart • Justin • Kristine • Paul • Ramona • Robert • Rolf • Samantha • Carmen

Tools	Personas using the tool
<p>Translation</p> <p>You can have a text in a foreign language translated into another language. Various languages are available for translation: English, French, German, Spanish, Swedish, Turkish, Russian, and Ukrainian.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Amir • Kristine • Ramona • Samantha • Carmen
<p>Content replacement</p> <p>On a website, substitute text or substitute information can be stored. When substitute text or substitute information is available, it will be displayed.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carmen

3.2 Editorial and Content-related Barriers

Editorial and content-related barriers "result from inadequate editorial or structural preparation of content and its adaptation for the internet" (Berger et al., 2011, p. 133). These barriers include difficult-to-understand language, lack of text structure, and similar issues.

Easy Reading can assist with these barriers using the following tools:

- Word explanation
- Symbol language
- Symbol search
- Reading aloud
- Translation

Profile of Amir

Name: Amir Abdel

Age: 18 years old

Hobbies:

- Field hockey
- Meeting friends
- Designing caps

Character:

Amir is a very helpful teenager. He enjoys competitions and aims to win them. Amir does not always express his thoughts directly; he prefers to remain polite and considerate.

Media usage:

Amir uses a smartphone daily, primarily to stay in touch with his family and friends and to use various social media apps. He can use a PC or laptop in school and at the residential project where he lives.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading ruler

reading mode

symbol language

symbol search

translation

Life circumstances

Life:

Amir came to Germany with his cousin Omar from Syria. The parents of the two teenagers are not in Germany. Amir and Omar live in a residential project for unaccompanied minor refugees.

Primary contact persons:

- His cousin (Omar), who fled from Syria with him
- A staff member (Peter) at the residential project for unaccompanied minor refugees
- A teacher from school (Mrs. Meyer) who provides him with reading support

Education and career:

Amir had to drop out of school in Syria because he had to leave the country. Education is important to him, and he would like to study in Germany. His desired field of study is fashion design.

Digital barriers

Amir does not speak German very well (yet). He often loses his place in the text and is unfamiliar with German letters. Amir understands and speaks a little French, but not fluently, either.

(Participation) Desires

He wishes to stay in Germany and truly settle there. He wants to pursue higher education and is highly motivated to improve his German for more opportunities. He aspires to be more independent and less reliant on others.

Profile of Dieter

Name: Dieter Pilcher

Age: 24 years old

Hobbies:

- Being in nature
- Watching television
- Listening to music
- Going to concerts
- Sports (football, riding a bike)

Character:

Dieter is a warm and friendly person. He is very creative and ambitious. In new and unfamiliar situations, he is insecure.

Media usage:

Dieter enjoys watching television and has a smartphone that he primarily uses for making phone calls. He needs to work on a computer for his job.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

change font size

change line space

symbol language

symbol search

Life circumstances

Life:

Dieter has been living alone for two years. He has limited contact with his mother. He enjoys doing sports together with his best friend, Roland.

Primary contact persons:

- His close friend Roland, to whom he confides everything
- His older sister, who serves as a role model
- Teachers and fellow students at the VHS (Volkshochschule, a German adult education centre) that he visits twice a week

Education and career:

Dieter initially attended a regular school but transferred to a Förderschule (special needs school) at 11 years old. Since his graduation, he has had several part-time jobs, but none lasted long. Currently, he works as a temporary helper at an animal shelter.

Digital barriers

Dieter has dyslexia, which makes it challenging for him to read and write individual words. Reading articles online is difficult for him because he easily gets distracted by images and advertisements.

(Participation) Desires

Dieter wishes to be able to read longer texts independently eventually. This would allow him to pursue his interests more effectively, such as regularly staying informed about his favourite football team. Additionally, he would like to apply for an apprenticeship, for which reading and filling out forms online is necessary.

Profile of Justin

Name: Justin Bose

Age: 14 years old

Hobbies:

- Watching football
- Playing mobile games
- Borussia Dortmund (BVB)

Character:

Justin is open and helpful, and he can accept boundaries well. However, he struggles to empathize with others, often leading to communication problems and conflicts with those around him.

Media usage:

Justin spends a lot of time on his phone. His smartphone is "everything" to him. He chats with friends, makes plans, and is active on Facebook and Instagram. He can operate the smartphone well but struggles to acquire new digital skills.

Tools von Easy Reading:

reading aloud

word explanation

Life circumstances

Life:

Justin lives with his family. His older brother is a role model for him. He does not get along well with his younger sister. Justin has to share his room with his little sister, so he often lacks a place to retreat.

Primary contact persons:

- His best school friend, Torben. He feels comfortable at Torben's home and gets the peace often lacking at his own home. Justin and Torben spend a lot of time on their smartphones together, chatting with girls from their class.

Education and career:

Justin is in the 6th grade at Hildegardis-Schule, a special education school with a focus on learning in Dortmund. He enjoys workshop classes but dislikes German and textile classes.

Digital barriers

Although Justin cannot (yet) read well, he can still navigate the internet. With his smartphone, he can have web content read aloud to him, and he sends chat messages using the voice recording function. His online activities are purely recreational. He is unfamiliar and does not want to use applications that could assist him in daily life or learning.

(Participation) Desires

Justin wishes to understand the internet better because many websites contain much text and are, therefore, challenging for him to comprehend. His teachers say he can also use the internet for learning, such as researching for school.

Profile of Lisa

Name: Lisa Nowak

Age: 13 years old

Hobbies:

- Handball
- Listening to music
- Cooking and baking

Character:

Lisa is friendly, open, and communicative. She is curious and likes to try new things. However, her tolerance for frustration is low.

Media usage:

Lisa uses the family's laptop with the support of her parents or Charlotte (family assistant) to listen to music or watch videos. On TV, she watches handball games, series, and shows.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

symbol language

symbol search

image search

Life circumstances

Life:

Lisa lives with her mother, father, and older brother in a single-family home in Essen. Her mother is from Russia, and her father was born in Germany.

Primary contact persons:

- Her family, especially her parents and her brother Christian, the family assistant and school companion, with whom Lisa spends a lot of time.
- Teachers, classmates, and friends with whom Lisa spends her school and free time.

Education and career:

Lisa is currently attending the 6th grade of an inclusive secondary school. There, she is supported by her school companion, Charlotte.

Digital barriers

Lisa has a cognitive impairment. As a result, her reading, writing, and mathematical abilities are weak, and she has difficulty reading texts online. She cannot filter out irrelevant information and is easily distracted. She struggles to distinguish between what is important and what is not.

(Participation) Desires

Lisa wishes for more independence and more active participation in groups. She wants to use her skills more in social situations. She would like to bake a new recipe from the internet because she wants to bring homemade cake or cookies to her class on her birthday.

Profile of Samantha

Name: Samantha Thöne

Age: 9 years old

Hobbies:

- Dancing
- Singing
- Crafting
- Watching BVB games
- Playing with her friends

Character:

Samantha is curious and open-minded. She enjoys meeting new people and talking to them. Samantha has many good friends, even though she can sometimes be a bit impatient.

Media usage:

Samantha uses a tablet with the support of her parents to listen to music, watch the latest music videos, and look up song lyrics. She enjoys watching soccer games and TV shows.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading mode

reading aloud

reading ruler

word explanation

translation

Life circumstances

Life:

Samantha lives with her mothers, Lara and Jessica, and her younger sister, Lisa, in Erwitte. Her grandparents live in Erwitte and Cologne.

Primary contact persons:

- Her family, especially her parents, sister, and grandparents from Erwitte
- Teachers, classmates and friends
- Her best friend Tim

Education and career:

Samantha attends the fourth grade of elementary school. She is a dedicated student and is interested in various subjects. Soon, it will be decided which secondary school Samantha will attend. She hopes to continue going to school with Tim.

Digital barriers

Samantha is currently learning to read. She still faces some challenges that take up a lot of her time and energy. She finds reading unfamiliar words difficult and it is hard for her to not lose her focus in the text. When reading texts online, she quickly loses concentration because she is easily distracted by advertisements. In the long run, her motivation to read might suffer.

(Participation) Desires

Samantha wants to navigate the internet without the help of adults. She wants to look up song lyrics online so she can sing along to her favourite songs and new hits from the radio. Unfortunately, many of the songs are in English. This makes it difficult for her to understand the lyrics.

Profile of Jutta

Name: Jutta Jenkins

Age: 34 years old

Hobbies:

- Cultivating vegetables in her parents' garden
- Biking in the summer
- Watching movies in the cinema

Character:

Jutta is an ambitious and cheerful woman. She is interested in many things and wants to continue her education and personal development.

Media usage:

Jutta has a smartphone. She mainly uses it to chat with her friends and family. She likes to follow some influencers on social media and looks at the pictures her friends post. She can use her sister's computer whenever she wants.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

Life circumstances

Life:

Jutta lives with her sister in a small apartment in the city centre. She regularly meets up with her friends and goes on short trips with them.

Primary contact persons:

- Her parents
- Her sister
- Her colleagues from the workshop for people with disabilities
- Her circle of friends

Education and career:

She works in the administration department of sheltered workshop for people with disabilities. She enjoys her work and gets along well with her colleagues. She is currently trying to find a job on the primary labour market.

Digital barriers

Jutta has dyslexia and difficulties understanding complex texts. This makes reading very challenging for her, especially on the internet. On websites, she is easily distracted from the text by advertisements and too many images.

(Participation) Desires

She wants to independently search for job listings that interest her on her sister's computer.

3.3 Barriers due to design

Barriers due to design arise from errors in design. "Examples include too low contrasts, background images, too small font sizes, etc." (Berger et al., 2011, p. 133). Easy Reading can fix these barriers with the following tools:

- Contrast
- Font size
- Line spacing
- Reading mode
- Reading ruler

Profile of Eberhart

Name: Eberhart Hofmann

Age: 49 years old

Hobbies:

- Listening to music
- Reading
- Recreational sports group, cycling, going for a walk

Character:

After moving to the residential group, Eberhart took some time to adjust to the new situation. Meanwhile, he has become more communicative, participates in group evenings, and increasingly turns to his primary caregiver with questions. However, he also likes to spend time alone and in nature.

Media usage:

Because of his walks, Eberhart is supposed to get a mobile phone so he can reach someone in case of an emergency.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading mode

reading ruler

word explanation

Life circumstances

Life:

Eberhart has been living in an external, residential group for people with intellectual disabilities for a year. He works in a sheltered workshop for people with disabilities. In his free time, he participates in a sports group with great passion.

Primary contact persons:

- His mother passed away four years ago; his father lives in a nursing home
- His older sister visits him regularly
- His primary caregiver from the residential group, Leonie
- He gets along well with his roommates and his work colleagues

Education and career:

Eberhart attended a special education school. He works in a sheltered workshop for people with disabilities in the crafts sector.

Digital barriers

Eberhart has noticed that the library, where he likes to look at books or borrow CDs, has changed its lending system. He needs to renew his library card and can only do this online. The borrowing process can now also be done online. Since Eberhart has no experience with the Internet, he asks his primary caregiver for help.

(Participation) Desires

Eberhart wants to learn how to use the library's online catalogue and how to apply for a new card.

Profile of Gerda

Name: Gerda Vogelweid

Age: 85 years old

Hobbies:

- Listening to music
- Playing the piano
- Reading crime novels
- Enjoying nature

Character:

Gerda is a cheerful and sociable; she is always open to new things. She is religious and goes to church every week. She likes to solve her everyday problems on her own. She quickly becomes insecure and agitated if something does not work out as she imagined.

Media usage:

Gerda received a smartphone as a gift from her children, but rarely uses it. She also has a PC in her room.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading ruler

change colour

Enlarge/reduce font size

Life circumstances

Life:

Gerda lives in Unna and feels very comfortable there. When her husband died a few years ago, she considered moving to the senior centre because she is a very sociable person and does not like spending time alone. Her children and grandchildren live nearby and often visit her.

Primary contact persons:

- Her family, including her two children and her grandchildren
- Roommates and staff at the senior centre

Education and career:

Gerda used to work part-time and was always busy with work, children, and household chores. She enjoys having more time now for her hobbies and the things she finds fun.

Digital barriers

She has an age-related vision impairment. Moreover, she finds concentrating increasingly difficult and has trouble remembering new things over an extended period. Due to her hurried nature, she often makes careless mistakes. Her smartphone and proficiently handling the PC are still very challenging for her.

(Participation) Desires

Gerda has always been independent and would like to remain so. If necessary, she is willing to accept help. She wants to use her smartphone more to stay in touch with her distant family. She also wants to try reading an e-book.

Profile of Kristine

Name: Kristine Tischner

Age: 35 years old

Hobbies:

- Dance group
- Going to the movies
- Spending time with friends

Character:

Kristine is a friendly and open young woman. She is proud of the independence she has achieved so far and wants to build on it further.

Media usage:

She stays in contact with friends through Facebook, regularly talks on the phone with her parents and her aunt and keeps herself informed about new movies in theatres.

Tools of Easy Reading:

read aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

word explanation

translation

Life circumstances

Life:

Kristine lives in a semi-independent living group with support. She is in regular contact with her family. Every two weeks, Kristine is visited by her parents. Kristine likes meeting with her friends to watch romantic comedies at the cinema together. Every Tuesday and Thursday, Kristine practices with her dance group for performances.

Primary contact persons:

- Her parents and her aunt
- Primary support worker Anja (residential facility)
- Work colleagues Lina and Jessica

Education and career:

Kristine works in a sheltered workshop for people with disabilities. She and her colleagues are responsible for the gardening department.

Digital barriers

Kristine has difficulties finding current performances on her dance group's website and often cannot determine if there are any schedule changes. She would like to delve deeper into current movies and actors/actresses. However, she struggles to concentrate when reading articles online because of the overwhelming advertisements and pop-ups. Also, a lot of these articles are in English.

(Participation) Desires

Kristine wants to share information about current movies with others without having to ask for help. She wants to tell her parents and her aunt when her dance group's performances are. For this, she would like to look up the dates once verbally communicated to her.

Profile of Paul

Name: Paul Jakobsen

Age: 17 Jahre

Hobbies:

- Politics
- Cars
- Pets
- Shows

Character:

Paul is a curious and open-minded teenager who is very tech-savvy. He usually finds it easy to adapt to new digital techniques. Paul is very curious and loves to learn more about his diverse interests. However, he can also react impulsively and is easily irritable.

Media usage:

Paul has a smartphone that he uses daily. At school, he uses a PC and at home, he has a laptop on which he mainly watches Netflix shows.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading mode

reading aloud

reading ruler

word explanation

Life circumstances

Life:

Paul lives with his brother and mother in Dortmund. His mother often has to work long hours, but Paul gets along very well with his brother, and they often watch the latest TV shows together.

Primary contact person:

- His family, especially his mother and brother
- His father and uncle, who do not live with him.
- His friends at school

Education and career:

Paul is still in school and has not yet graduated. He attends a computer club at school, which he enjoys.

Digital barriers

Paul has learning difficulties. He struggles with focus and retention over extended periods. Reading is challenging for him, especially with long texts without pictures, causing him to lose track quickly. As a result, he often struggles to keep up in class.

(Participation) Desires

Paul wishes that digital content was presented in a more structured manner and included pictures and explanations. He would like an alternative to sifting through pages of text. This way, he would find learning about his interests more enjoyable and less draining.

Profile of Ramona

Name: Ramona Müller

Age: 22 years old

Hobbies:

- Watching television
- Going out with friends

Character:

Ramona is a warm and friendly person. She is very creative and ambitious. In new and unfamiliar situations, she feels uncertain.

Media usage:

Ramona enjoys watching TV and has a smartphone that she primarily uses for calling or voice messages. For her additional qualification, Ramona needs to re-search on the computer.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

word explanation

translation

Life circumstances

Life:

Ramona has been living alone for two years. She does not know her father, and has regular but rather superficial contact with her mother. She meets her friend Lara at the café across from her apartment every Saturday.

Primary contact persons:

- Her close friend Lara
- Her neighbours with whom she shares the garden for communal activities
- She gets along well with the teachers and classmates at the vocational college

Education and career:

Ramona initially attended a secondary school (Realschule) but switched to a primary school (Hauptschule) at 12. Since graduating, she has been working part-time as a domestic helper for elderly people. Currently, she attends a vocational college and is pursuing an additional qualification in the healthcare sector.

Digital barriers

Ramona has dyslexia. It takes a lot of effort for her to read and write individual words. The many distractions on the internet, such as images and advertisements, make reading more difficult for her.

(Participation) Desires

Ramona hopes to be able to read longer texts independently eventually. Moreover, she would like to apply for a training position in a care facility for older people, and for that, it is necessary to read and fill out online forms. In addition, she needs support in searching for a suitable internship position.

Profile of Robert

Name: Robert Mayer

Age: 86 Jahre

Hobbies:

- Reading
- Cooking
- Watching television
- Cards and board games

Character:

Robert is open, friendly, and communicative. However, he has been experiencing increasing communication difficulties and has been forgetful lately.

Media usage:

Robert uses traditional media like radio, television, and newspapers. He rarely uses the computer and only reads newspaper articles on the internet.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading aloud

reading mode

reading ruler

change colours

change font size

increase/reduce line spacing

word explanation

Life circumstances

Life:

Robert lives in a nursing home. His children and grandchildren live farther away and visit him irregularly.

Primary contact persons:

- Nursing and assistance staff (Ben) in the nursing home
- His friend Peter, with whom he regularly plays cards
- Doctors he visits for regular check-ups
- Children and grandchildren with whom he speaks on the phone weekly

Education and career:

Robert worked as a journalist for 30 years and is now retired. He always passionately pursued his profession and retired with a heavy heart.

Digital barriers

Robert was recently diagnosed with mild to moderate dementia. As a result of the illness, Robert easily gets distracted by irrelevant information. The numerous impressions on the internet quickly lead to sensory overload and overwhelm for him.

(Participation) Desires

Robert wishes for more security in his daily life. He wants to engage more in social interactions. He wishes always to be informed about current political and social events for meaningful conversations.

Profile of Rolf

Name: Rolf Reusch

Age: 30 years old

Hobbies:

- Listening to music
- Going to concerts
- Going on walks
- Creative work with wood and paper

Character:

Rolf is a friendly and very creative person. In his spare time, he likes to engage in artistic activities. He approaches people openly and actively. He might come off as pushy to some, but he genuinely wants to be helpful.

Media usage:

Rolf shares a computer with his father. He also has a mobile phone so he can call his parents.

Tools of Easy Reading:

reading mode

word explanation

symbol language

symbol search

Life circumstances

Life:

Rolf lives with his parents and is well-integrated into the neighbourhood. His parents have renovated the first floor of their house to provide him with a small apartment. His parents and an outpatient care service, which visits him once a week for two hours, assist him with daily tasks.

Primary contact persons

- His parents
- His colleagues Andi and Olaf and his supervisor Heinz
- His care and assistance provider Anna

Education and career:

Rolf attended a special education school. Currently, he works in a sheltered workshop for people with disabilities in the metal department.

Digital barriers

Rolf regularly uses his father's computer. He enjoys it a lot but often forgets how to operate it, for example, how to access websites. His father does not always have the time to assist him with the PC operation, so he enrolled him in a computer course, which Rolf happily attends.

(Participation) Desires

Rolf would like to have his own computer. His parents want him to become more confident in using the internet before they buy him a PC. Rolf wants to show his parents that he can become more independent using the PC and the internet.

Profile of Gertrud

Name: Gertrud Rössing

Age: 62 years old

Hobbies:

- Likes to go to yoga classes at her gym
- Has been knitting for many years with pleasure, today she knits with the help of a magnifying glass

Character:

Gertrud has been practicing her profession with passion for many years. She enjoys working with children and tries to continue her education. She enjoys her life as a grandmother since her granddaughter was born last year.

Media usage:

Gertrud received a laptop from her daughter for Christmas. She wants to be able to use digital media in order to keep up with the times.

Tools of Easy Reading:

change colour

change font size

Life circumstances

Life:

Gertrud lives with her husband, Johannes, in a semi-detached house. She commutes to work by bicycle and loves her profession very much. Last year, her granddaughter Lea-Sophie was born.

Primary contact persons:

- Her husband, Johannes
- Her daughter Larissa, her son-in-law Maximilian, and the little granddaughter Lea-Sophie
- Her colleagues, especially her friend Judith
- Her friends from the knitting café, which she visits twice a week

Education and career:

Gertrud loves her profession very much. She enjoys working with young people and welcomes the various challenges that her job presents. She wants to continue her independence as a child caregiver until retirement.

Digital barriers

Gertrud does not always navigate new media well. Due to an age-related eye disease, she can read enlarged and high-contrast text better. Navigating websites is often very challenging for her, as websites are individually designed visually.

(Participation) Desires

She would like to independently research new ideas for children's games in order to stay "up-to-date".

3.4 Organization and Environment

The implementation of new technologies, such as Easy Reading, must involve a variety of professional groups. What it means to employ Easy Reading is outlined with the personas of Carmen, a teacher, and Uta, an IT representative in a disability assistance facility. These personas are structured somewhat differently. They tend to describe questions and application scenarios that could be relevant for the respective person.

Profile of Carmen

Name: Carmen Borsbach

Age: 41 years old

Profession:

- Teacher of German and English at an inclusive secondary school
- Homeroom teacher of class 5a

Character:

Carmen is a dedicated special education teacher. She wants to support her students in the best possible way. To this end, she is keen on continuing her education and tries to stay up-to-date with new didactic approaches and media.

Media usage:

Carmen uses her laptop, her cell phone, and occasionally a tablet in her daily life. In class, Carmen likes to use the school PCs to assign research tasks to her students.

Tools of Easy Reading:

word explanation

translation

content replacement

Workday routine

Special education teacher:

As a special education teacher, Carmen is responsible for students with special educational needs at a secondary school. She prepares differentiated lessons and creates support plans.

Homeroom teacher:

In her class, there are currently five students with a focus on support for learning or language. However, there are also students in her class who are learning German as a second language.

Subject teacher:

Carmen is a teacher of English and German. In her subject teaching, she needs to prepare and differentiate the learning content so that all pupils can work on the same content despite different levels.

Barriers and challenges

Currently, Carmen's greatest challenge is adapting the subject content so that all children can work on it. The effort required to create materials for different levels of learning and different language abilities is very high. Furthermore, Carmen faces the challenge of being unable to always answer all students' questions.

(Participation) Desires

Carmen wishes to meet her student's needs. She wants to find effective and efficient ways to provide differentiated learning content with digital media. She also desires to provide targeted support impulses and additional tasks that students can work on more independently.

Profile of Uta

Name: Uta König

Age: 37 years old

Education and career:

Uta has completed training as an IT systems clerk and has been working for several years as an IT representative at a large facility for people with disabilities.

Media usage:

Uta regularly uses her smartphone. As part of her professional activities, she spends a lot of time on the computer.

Activity Profile:

- Inventory of previous activities regarding IT security
- Establishment, operation, and further development of the IT security organization
- Contact person for IT security matters for colleagues
- Monitoring and assessment of new acquisitions or installation of software and the like
- Initiation of projects and training on the topic of digitalization

Clarification Needed for New Software

Questions that need to be addressed before new software can be installed:

- What licensing models does the software operate under?
- Regarding data protection: What user data are collected or forwarded?
- On which devices can/must software be installed?
- How compatible is the software with programs already in use?
- Is internet access required?
- How can the software be sustainably established in the facility (e.g., staff training)?

Desires

Uta considers it important that the facility and the people who work there are protected from hacking attacks. She also deems it crucial that applications that could potentially harm the devices are not installed haphazardly, as she is responsible for maintaining all the devices. Nevertheless, she wants to enable the people in the facility to download all the necessary applications required for their daily work.

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Concluding Remarks

The personas presented here are the work results of the project's first months and a selection of potentially relevant personas. Additional personas developed during the project will be included in a subsequent edition of the persona catalogue.

Contact

Authors:

- Vanessa Heitplatz [ORCID 0000-0002-1222-9246](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1222-9246)
- Nele Maskut [ORCID 0000-0003-0200-2723](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0200-2723)
- Leevke Wilkens [ORCID 0000-0002-9028-3010](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9028-3010)
- Miriam Bursy [ORCID 0000-0002-8723-4437](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8723-4437)
- Marie-Christin Lueg [ORCID 0000-0001-7401-4526](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7401-4526)
- Luisa Kramschneider [ORCID 0009-0001-2688-6917](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-2688-6917)
- Lukas Baumann [ORCID 0000-0002-8100-3988](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8100-3988)
- Susanne Dirks [ORCID 0000-0003-1055-5379](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1055-5379)

Translation and assistance:

Samira Erdmann

EVE4all-Project

TU Dortmund University

Department of Rehabilitation Technology

Emil-Figge-Straße 50

44227 Dortmund

eve4all.rt.fk13@tu-dortmund.de

EVE4all – Easy Understanding for Everyone

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Excluding the aforementioned graphics of the personas and the cover page.

GEFÖRDERT VOM

